

Being, *technonihil* and ethics as a three-valued model

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Abstract

In a mechanistic view, living beings are bodies and their vital movements tend to self-preservation. A subset of living being, human being, employs technique to preserve itself. Thus, technique sustains being in its function as the soul of becoming of the human being entity. In this way, technique is capable of moving humanity to ever new scenarios, overcoming the community rules and habits of a given period. This overrun leads to an absence of laws, reference points and experience gained within the communities: *technonihil* (or *technomeden*). Political work must critically judge, control and limit *technonihil*, with ethical and moral judgment on every technological advances.

Keywords : technique; *technonihil*; ethics; political effort.

Many philosophers have made attempts to describe human being from physics and ontology up to the ethics and politics. With the risk of oversimplification, some examples of philosophers are given herein: The Milesian philosophers, the Pythagoreans, Plato, Hobbes, Spinoza, Leibniz, and Kropotkin.

The members of the Ionian school, or Milesian school, were called by Aristotle *physiologoi* (φυσιολόγοι) since they were discussing on *physis* (φύσις). A discussion of *physis* should not be considered a mere investigation of nature, but the search for the general characteristics of reality (Trabattoni, 2008). Some philosophers, as for example Costanzo Preve, highlight that Thales, Anaximander, Anaximenes, were trying to find a principle (*arche*, ἀρχή) in order to organize a rational legislation. Actually, Costanzo Preve stresses the concept mentioning the “indefinite” (Apeiron, ἄπειρον) by Anaximander as a metaphor for the infiniteness of personal wealth to be countered through the use of proper division (*nemein*, νέμειν) to safeguard the community (Preve, 2015). Preve's relief is commendable, although it should not be confined to Anaximander alone, as all the Milesians were concerned with using this reasoning method to investigate reality.

The principle for the Pythagoreans is number, which allows them to find laws that describe reality. Number, as a principle, constitutes the world, a proportionate and ordered cosmos. From this cosmological assumption, the Pythagoreans claim that the soul is harmony of the corporeal elements.

For Plato, ideas (essences) really exist, and the sensible world is but a copy. The most important idea is the idea of good, and Plato's idea of good recalls Pythagorean order and proportion. The idea of the good allows Plato to construct a theory about moral values, i.e., an axiology. The golden mean between two excesses proposed by Plato descends from the idea of good which is order and proportion. Plato has Socrates say in the *Philebus*:

Socrates: Therefore, if we are unable to capture the good in a single form, we may comprehend it with these: beauty, symmetry and truth. Let us declare that the three may properly be regarded as a single element responsible for the condition of the mixture, and that the mixture becomes good because of this.

(Plato, *Philebus*, 65A) (Plato, n.d.)

For Thomas Hobbes, everything is matter: Living beings, objects and thoughts are “bodies.” Within this mechanistic framework, the vital movements of animated bodies tend to self-preservation. For human being, avoiding death is the most important thing, but, since everyone has rights on everything (*ius in omnia*), people's actions will unavoidably conflict. To avoid a state of war, people should accept a contract that includes the constitution of a society (*pactum unionis*) and the delegation of the power to a sovereignty (*pactum subiectionis*). In this way, sovereignty, with its monopoly of violence, pledges self-preservation, but also a place for art and industry (Chevallier, 1949; Hobbes, 1651; Scotognella, 2020).

Baruch Spinoza, in the masterpiece *Ethica, ordine geometrico demonstrata*, has developed a theory of extreme immanence: If substance needs nothing else to exist, then only God is substance. In this framework, all entities, including human being (extended and thinking mode of the eternal substance), are modes of the eternal substance (Spinoza, 1677). In an ultimate effort at

simplification, the highest good in such deterministic universe, which is intellectual love of God, is strengthening together in the intuitive identification of the human-mode with God (Sini, 2013).

Leibniz divides substance into simple metaphysical units: monads. Each monad mirrors the whole, and God is the supreme monad that best perceives the universe. God creates the universe by finding the optimum between absolute freedom and moral perfection.

Kropotkin employs an inductive/deductive method to demonstrate mutual aid among living beings. Reworking Darwin's studies and findings in an original way, Kropotkin proposes a description of organized societies where mutual aid is the cornerstone for the goal of self-preservation. In this way, humanity does not need state organizations since mutual aid efficiently eliminates the need of sovereignty (Kropotkin, 1902). It is noteworthy that both Hobbes and Kropotkin start from a materialistic ontology, but they conjecture two very distant states of nature (Scotognella, 2020).

In this study, a three-valued model is proposed that starts from physical and ontological foundations and arrives at conclusions in the field of ethics. The three values are: i) being as becoming of the entities and the particular entity of human being that employs technique to preserve itself; ii) technique that continuously moves the human being towards new scenarios with a consequent creation of voids in the system of laws and norms that regulates the life of communities, i.e., *technonihil*; iii) ethical and political work of a community to reharmonize norms by incorporating technological advances.

First moment: Technique as soul of becoming of human being

In a mechanistic ontology, living beings are bodies and their vital movements tend to self-preservation. In this sentence there are already several issues. One may ask how this view fits into the context of materialism: One may ask whether everything, including inanimate objects and thoughts, is matter (Hobbes' materialism), adhering to monism, or whether some things are not matter, as in Gustavo Bueno's philosophical materialism in which the existence of incorporeal things such as distances between objects is asserted (Romero et al., 2022). Moreover, it is clear that the tendency of living beings for self-preservation can be read as a kind of finalism. Although, simple examples taken from the natural sciences can be proposed, such as the organization of herbivores in the different ecosystems of our planet: In order to survive predatory attacks, herbivores tend to organize themselves into herds, flocks etc.

Human being is the subset of living being that uses technique in order to preserve itself. Technique is used here in its broadest sense, including language, cooking, the manufacture of clothes, tools, and microprocessors. Thus, technique sustains being in its function as the soul of becoming of human being, recalling Heidegger's concept of being (Heidegger, 2019; Barzaghi, 2014).

Second moment: *technonihil* or *technomeden*

Technique, with the invention and development of new tools, completely change the world in which humanity lives; it is the *work*, devoted on the fabrication of durable objects, described by Hannah

Arendt in *The Human Condition* (Arendt, 1998), but also the recent development of software that are more and more useful for a multiplicity of things.

These changes lead to a complete lack for human beings: lack of a system of laws and norms, lack of reference points in daily life, lack of a set of prior knowledge for social life and work. We can summarize this condition with the term *technonihil*: perception of lack of everything, total emptiness (*nihil*, nothing), induced by technological advancement. A similar term can be *technomeden*, which is the union of τέχνη and μηδέν. Thus, the term *technonihil* (or *technomeden*) emphasizes the rapid changes that are due to innovative technologies, which are too fast to be followed by society.

Examples of *technonihil* can be: i) the introductions in the market of things (tools, drugs etc.) that lead to unexpected damages to people and the state does not have an ensemble of laws and rights that protect such people; ii) the recent arise of digital labor platforms that finds not enough protected workers (European Commission. Joint Research Centre., 2020; Scotognella, 2022a, 2022b). Another vivid example is depicted in the film *I, Daniel Blake* by Ken Loach (*I, Daniel Blake*, 2016), in which the welfare system is completely automatized and online and many people are unable to master it (Furlan Brighente, 2022).

[Another interesting term is the term *technoanomie*, which has been introduced in a pioneering work published in 2002 by Francesco Macarone Palmieri in a different context (Macarone Palmieri, 2002). In order not to create overlap, the term *technonihil* has been preferred in this study]

Third moment: ethical effort to harmonize laws and technological advances

Technonihil / *technomeden* is the lack of laws, reference points, and prior knowledge in a given period and in a given society due to the technological advancement.

In order to limit *technonihil*, an ethical and political work should be pursued. The community should study itself to understand if there is possibility to harmonize the systems of laws and norms of the community with the new technologies, in particular by developing new laws that protect the people of the community. Moreover, the research community can contribute to limiting the *technonihil* / *technomeden* by supporting legislators and citizens with a better comprehension of the scientific advancements. For example, it is very important that works of several researchers on public acceptance of technological innovations are already reported in the literature (Gupta et al., 2012). Remarkable examples are the work on the social acceptance of food technologies (Siegrist, 2008), recycled water (Fielding et al., 2019), renewable energy (Devine-Wright, 2007; Heras-Saizarbitoria et al., 2011; Trifonova, 2022), and robotics (Gaudiello et al., 2016; Savela et al., 2018). Such studies, *ab imis fundamentis*, should involve philosophic aspects, economic aspects, socio-psychologic aspects, but also the point of view of science, technology, engineering, and science (STEM). Given the need for critical technology judgement, knowledge sharing is very important. For this, the fundamental role of education is evident: i) to teach the scientific community the ability to communicate the full potential of their research; ii) to bring society up to date in the use of new technologies; iii) to stimulate critical judgement of technologies throughout society. Consequently, the delicate function of education in a state organization should be performed by a power that is separated from the legislative, executive, and judicial powers.

Conclusion

Human being is the subset of living being that uses technique to preserve itself. The employment of technique continuously changes the world around people with new tools. The communities can be bewildered by new technologies, and this can lead to technonihil, or technomeden. Thus, an ethical and political work, strongly supported by education, should be pursued to limit technonihil / technomeden. The rationale presented in this work is based on a three-valued model, which recalled Hegel's dialectics:

In point of form Logical doctrine has three sides: (α) the Abstract side, or that of understanding; (β) the Dialectical, or that of negative reason; (γ) the Speculative, or that of positive reason. (Hegel, Encyclopaedia of the Philosophical Sciences, § 79) (Hegel et al., 2010)

Gives an attempt of method that can be used to describe some situations in the history of human being, but also to prescribe the endeavors of societies, in particular politicians and researchers, to better harmonize the collective life and the technological advancements.

Methodology

A literature review on the efforts of several philosophers, in attempting at describe human being from physics and ontology up to the ethics and politics, has been pursued. Then, a speculative rationale divided in three moments that connect human being that uses technique to preserve itself, the technique that gives rise to technonihil / technomeden, and the ethical and political effort that should limit technonihil / technomeden, is given.

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